

**PAPERS ON LIBERTY
AND SECURITY IN
EUROPE**

A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF THE EU'S REGULAR MIGRATION SYSTEM

**Objectifying, structurally
discriminatory and not aligned with
basic EU and international standards**

Anjum Shabbir

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Policy Brief largely draws from the key findings of an [EU-level report](#) produced for the EU-funded [AspirE project](#), and interviews held with EU officials within the context of this project. It focuses on policy issues impacting the EU's current regular migration policy on how people who are not from an EU country – third country nationals – can move to and stay in the EU through legal channels. It shows that EU policy goals combined with the specific way they are expressed under EU law result in some main policy problems. In short, a system has been created that:

- objectifies third country nationals and embeds structural discrimination against them;
- is made up of an overly complex and fragmented *acquis* of law that goes against the principles of transparency, legal certainty, and legal clarity (i.e. the quality of a law), which is very difficult for a third country national to follow and understand;
- does not sufficiently meet certain core and basic EU and international legal standards that third country nationals who have moved to the EU should benefit from and so that they can have agency over their own lives. For example, the right to human dignity, non-discrimination, decent working conditions, facilitated transitions and social cohesion; and
- can be an indirect cause of a third country national falling into a state of irregular migration.

This Policy Brief includes recommendations for a more humanising approach that the AspirE project has adopted. This approach considers third country nationals as individuals with rights and agency over their own lives.

In particular, the Policy Brief recommends that the EU:

- monitors compliance with its own standards and ILO decent work standards so that third country nationals can live with fewer legal constraints and experience less discrimination;
- develops a horizontal instrument codifying EU legal migration rules through the lens of 'fair treatment' for third country nationals in line with the EU Charter rights that apply to them; and
- includes more humanitarian exceptions and facilitated status transitions, in line with the objectives of the UN's Global Compact on Migration.

For a more detailed overview of these recommendations, please go to the end of this Policy Brief.

Keywords: regular migration; objectification; selectivity; fragmentation; sectorial approach; hierarchy of rights; lack of 'fair treatment'; structural discrimination; indirect cause of irregularised migration

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AspirE (Asian prospects in (re)migration to/within the EU) is a three-year research project taking place from 2023-25 that examines the decision making of aspiring (re)migrants from selected Southeast and East Asian countries (China, Japan, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam) to and within selected EU member countries (Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Italy, and Portugal).

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Introduction

This Policy Brief presents specific policy challenges which have arisen due to an objectifying- instead of a humanising- policy approach of the EU in regular migration¹ matters. There is an overemphasis on policy goals that aim to obtain the greatest economic benefits to the EU in a way that treats many third country nationals as economic units and walking financial numbers – rather than individuals who deserve an equal level of rights, fundamental freedoms, and agency over their lives.

While there has always been a parallel EU policy goal of ensuring ‘fair treatment’ for third country nationals when compared to EU nationals to precisely protect them from pure objectification, it is not given as much weight. This is reflected in the translation of policy goals into law, where economically focused and utilitarian objectives have consistently been dominant.

The way that the EU regular migration framework has been designed – and continues to be designed – enables structural discrimination. The law is fragmented and sectorial (for example, following a worker-by-worker approach), which enables a very different set of obligations and rights to apply based on what kind of person the EU and its Member States find more ‘attractive’ and most desired. And the EU finds the wealthiest, most educated individuals the most attractive, disregarding the role all kinds of individuals in a socially healthy and cohesive society could play. Accordingly, these most desired individuals are granted the top level of rights in a hierarchy of rights once they are already living in the EU.

The EU has not only set up a highly customised, inherently discriminatory system, but has also made it very difficult for third country nationals to understand. This is not only due to the inherent complexity of split competences between the supranational and national levels that characterises EU law in this domain, but also due to the further splitting of competence in a way that masks legal accountability and impedes the principles of legal certainty and transparency. In short, the sectorial legislative instruments making up the framework overlap in some places, leave gaps in others, and are unclear in other respects.

Ensuring non-discrimination is not only lacking – EU policy does not live up to other universal protected rights, in particular rights for working migrants under both the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and other applicable international standards concerning permanent residency and integration, family life, and protection from labour exploitation. The very narrow construction of eligibility and rights, and the limited possibilities for third

¹ This Policy Brief refers to ‘regular migration’ instead of ‘legal migration’, in line with the United Nations, Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration (GCM), Morocco, 10 and 11 December 2018, UN Resolution 73/195.

country nationals to transition from one legal status to another, can also indirectly lead to individuals falling into irregular or undocumented situations. This is in stark contrast to a clearly stated Objective enshrined in the UN Global Compact on Migration to do the exact opposite.

Key findings

FINDING #1: There is an overemphasis on the policy goal of facilitating regular migration for the most ‘economically attractive’ and ‘highly skilled/talented’ third country nationals in an objectifying way. This is to the detriment of the policy goal of ‘fair treatment’ and the rights-based approach enshrined in the EU Treaties.

Since the EU was given a legal mandate under the Treaty of Amsterdam in May 1999 to develop legally binding and common EU regular migration rules, it has always had a few clear and specifically expressed economy and security-focused policy goals – to fulfil labour shortages, boost the EU economy, make the EU more competitive in ‘a global race for talent,’ and to strengthen security in the name of threats such as terrorism.

But from the outset there was also a twin-policy goal of ‘fair treatment’ – *fairness as equality* – which stems from the European Council’s [Tampere Conclusions](#) of 15-16 October 1999, calling for a ‘fair treatment paradigm’ for third country nationals legally residing in the EU in comparison to EU nationals. It set the goal of approximating their legal status as ‘near as possible’ to that of EU Member State nationals (paragraphs 18 and 21), and a ‘more vigorous integration policy’ with rights and obligations that are ‘comparable to those of EU citizens.’

When deciding how much weight the policy goal of ‘fair treatment’ should be given, and how it is expressed in law through a rights-based approach, the following must be considered:

- i) that the EU has been legally bound by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights since 2009, which constitutionalises and places individual and human dignity at the centre of EU action;
- ii) that the EU Charter includes EU-specific fundamental rights which are granted to *everyone* irrespective of migration status (see for example Articles 15 and 31); and
- iii) interconnected commitments made by the EU, as well as separately by Member States, to protect international labour and migration standards. For example, the EU concept of ‘fairness’ is directly informed by the right to *decent* work, which is bolstered by International Labour Organisation (ILO) standards, as well as the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), and

which Article 53 of the EU Charter itself refers to as crucial. Furthermore, the 'people-centred' UN Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration sets out Objective 7.23(h) to '[d]evelop accessible and expedient procedures that facilitate transitions from one status to another... so as to prevent migrants from falling into an irregular status².'

But this has not occurred in practice, and unequal treatment still persists. Considering the underlying rationale for the policy goal of 'fair treatment' (established goals, rights and standards including the right to human dignity, non-discrimination, decent working conditions, facilitated transitions and social cohesion), the EU's economy and security-focused policy goals are overemphasised and overprioritised to the detriment of third country nationals.

The prevailing economic emphasis remains the status quo from a historical perspective. From 1999 to 2009, the policy direction was mainly utilitarian, highly selective, demand-driven, highly dependent on the nationalist agendas of Member States' Interior Ministries and characterised by a prominently securitarian mindset after the 9/11 terrorist attacks³.

There was a shift when the EU Charter was given legally binding value in 2009, with the European Parliament becoming a co-legislator with the Council of the European Union, the European Commission becoming the formal policy agenda-setter, and a specific legal basis being created (Article 79 TFEU) to protect the rights of third country nationals.

However, **this did not change the resulting Commission policy from prioritising the economic objectives above other objectives to ensure more humane considerations in parallel.** In 2009, emphasis was still being placed on 'economic vitality', the need for global competitiveness, and to address both labour shortages and an ageing EU population that should be addressed by a flexible legal migration system that Member States still had control over⁴.

The lopsided weight attached to these policy goals continues today. This is first shown by the policy response to the findings of the Commission's [2019 Fitness Check](#) on the EU

²<https://www.ilo.org/global/lang--en/index.htm>; <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-economic-social-and-cultural-rights>; Article 53 of the EU Charter states : '*Nothing in this Charter shall be interpreted as restricting or adversely affecting human rights and fundamental freedoms as recognised, in their respective fields of application, by Union law and international law and by international agreements to which the Union or all the Member States are party, including the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, and by the Member States' constitutions*'. The Global Compact also draws on and refers to 'decent work' – see Objective 6.

³ S. Carrera, K. Eisele, P. Melin and Z. Vankova (2022).

⁴ K. Eisele (2013), '[Why come here if I can go there? Assessing the 'Attractiveness' of the EU's Blue Card for 'Highly Qualified' Immigrants](#)' No. 60, October 2013, CEPS Paper in Liberty and Security in Europe.

regular migration *acquis*. Even though the Fitness Check identified several limits, ineffectiveness, gaps, and barriers caused by a fragmented system, it decided to focus on enhancing existing legislation in line with the policy goal of attracting ‘talent and wealthier, highly educated’ third country nationals. The opportunity to address structural discrimination and the inaccessibility of the system in a way that protects the human rights of third country nationals was not pursued.

This is also starkly highlighted by the European Commission’s rhetoric that focused on the ‘EU economy and labour market needs and shortages’ when presenting its [2021 Work Programme](#), called a ‘talents and skills’ package. The further announcement in November 2023 for an ‘EU Talent Pool’ that aims to match employers with third country national-job seekers makes no mention of existing discrimination against or the shortfall in protecting legally residing third country nationals⁵.

These economy and security-focused policy goals are also visible in the EU’s tourism, student, and labour migration ‘sub’-policies. In an increasingly politically charged manner, tourism policy strongly favours the type of ‘mobility’ that provides an economic benefit to the EU in the form of tourists’ purchasing power and the employment opportunities it generates. Student and labour policies focus on making it easy only for the wealthiest and most educated to enter the EU. Labour policy also grants stronger rights on a sliding scale according to a third country national worker’s pre-existing privileges.

This is an example of its **objectifying approach**, using a system of selectivity in favour of those who are ‘economically attractive’, which can perpetuate existing inequality, contribute to global inequality, and disregards the role and rights of every member of society.

FINDING #2: The prevailing EU policy goal has been translated into a legal framework that remains so fragmented, highly customised, selective, and with a hierarchy of rights in favour of only the most ‘economically attractive’, that it amounts to structural discrimination.

The EU’s economy and security-focused policy goals have been translated into a corresponding legal framework that has been consistently designed and developed in a way that it is fragmented, sectorial, highly selective and tailored in favour of the most ‘economically attractive’ kind of regular migration.

⁵ See further the EU-level AspirE Report, S. Carrera and A. Shabbir, [Humanising EU Migration Policies Transitioning of statuses under EU legal migration and labour mobility law and policy](#) (February 2024), section 2.4, pp. 10-11.

This fragmentation was catalysed early on. When the legal mandate for a common policy was granted to the EU in 1999, there was already fierce resistance from Member States' Interior Ministries⁶. This led to the failure of a key [European Commission proposal](#) in 2001 which would have resulted in a single 'horizontal' legislative initiative for a Directive covering all categories of third country national workers, irrespective of labour sector and skills/talents.

Instead, the European Commission chose to pursue [a partitioning strategy](#) that split the original proposal into separate pieces of legislation covering separate EU-defined categories of third country national workers with differing sets of rights and living/working conditions. This was despite the EESC's [warning](#) (see point 2.1.4) that a sectoral approach favouring highly skilled migrants would be discriminatory in nature and the European Parliament's [view](#) (see point 26) that there should be an overall (rather than sectoral) regulatory framework of reference.

A similar attempt was made in 2010 when the Commission attempted to bypass the sectoral approach by suggesting an Immigration Code. But the idea was never even officially presented and failed before the proposal phase, apparently due to the Commission's own perceptions and fears that some Member States would be highly reticent⁷.

The resulting legal framework is separated into sub-policies based on the purpose of legal migration. A few are selected for discussion in line with the AspirE project's focus – namely for tourism, employment, study, family reunification, and investment. This is important because it enables more favourable or privileged treatment for some people over others at the outset, such as an individual who offers more economic benefits than others.

However, treating *some* third country nationals more favourably than others without a legitimate justification for the difference in treatment is unlawful. Looking first for example at EU visa policy, it is selective in a highly customised way to determine which third country nationals can enter the EU according to the *nationality* a third country national has. While selectivity as a migration management tool is usual, and differential treatment based on nationality has been interpreted to enable states to regulate international cross-border human movements, there is a very thin and overlapping line between restrictions based on migration management goals and those indirectly impacting the national origin of aspiring migrants (see section 3.5, p. 27 of the AspirE project's [EU-level report](#)).

⁶ S. Carrera, K. Eisele, P. Melin and Z. Vankova (2022), p. 9.

⁷ S. Carrera, K. Eisele, P. Melin and Z. Vankova (2022).

Labour migration policy

Concerning EU labour migration policy, those third country nationals who do not fit the narrow criteria are further subject to eligibility conditions before they are granted entry into the EU, which narrows the categories further. These conditions are different according to the type of work and the EU-defined reason as to why they are entering. Salary thresholds, economic independence and self-sufficiency, and other migration-related eligibility conditions put a disproportionate emphasis on the wealth status of non-EU nationals aspiring to enter, reside, and work in the Union.

Only very narrowly defined kinds of working third country nationals can regularly move to the EU for specific employment purposes – Blue Card holders, intra-corporate transferees (ICTs) and seasonal workers. The very narrow criteria can lead to the problem that there are people who have the professional experience and skills to enter with a Blue Card, but their qualifications may not be recognised, leading them to instead apply through the only other available route – as a seasonal worker.

Illustrative of the structural discrimination is that in terms of characteristics, it can be presumed that the [Blue Card Directive](#) regime targets working age individuals who have completed their university studies – so usually older than 20-21 years old. Where there may be better higher education opportunities for men than women in the country of origin, the requirement to have higher education qualifications and even more so to have five years of equivalent professional experience may rule out many women, especially women of a certain age and working mothers. In turn this might mean women from some certain third countries – such as Japan – might see an advantage compared to those, for example, from Pakistan. The same may apply to social class if that is a barrier to access education and to work in the country of origin.

Similarly, the EU's [Intra-Corporate Transferees Directive](#) does not hide the fact that it was designed for multinationals – employers that can afford to be established in one or more foreign countries, which can lead to inherent discrimination. ICTs who are legally resident in the US, Japan, China, India, and Australia – where most multinationals are located – may have an advantage over, for example, those from the Philippines and Vietnam. Given the need for a connection to a multinational, those from a lower social class or with minority characteristics might be excluded if recruitment practices are discriminatory in the third country.

The narrow rules under the [Seasonal Workers Directive](#) lead to the targeting of certain worker profiles and the exclusion of others. The temporality rules imply that there is a targeting of, or preference for, third country nationals who are younger and do not have dependants – presumably targeting young single, parentless people. Given the nature of

the work, and because unlike the Blue Card Directive, there is no requirement for a certain level of professional qualifications, in practice it tends to cover those who work in manual labour who have not completed higher education and thus do not have higher education skills and qualifications – whether they did not want to, were not able to, did not have access to funds or could not complete their studies for any reason. This category of persons likely includes those from lower social classes. The Directive likely also excludes minors, the very old, and the physically unable. By avoiding vulnerable and minority categories, EU policy can then avoid having to provide long-term rights and benefits.

Then there is also a lopsided emphasis in the legal rules, which reveals that there is a hierarchy of rights which amounts to discrimination in favour of those who are already privileged, namely highly skilled and educated people who are paid high salaries, as opposed to low-paid, blue collar, medium/lower-skilled, and more socially and economically disadvantaged persons. There is a kind of sliding scale in how long those who are covered by EU labour migration law can legally work and reside on EU territory, and in the extent of the rights they have.

Third country nationals falling under the EU status of ‘seasonal workers’ have the fewest rights, in a way that is below the threshold of ILO standards and the right to decent work. For ICTs, it must be noted that they are substantively treated similarly to Blue Card holders but described as a ‘temporary’ migrant in a way that seems untrue given that they have much stronger rights than seasonal workers who are also described as ‘temporary migrants’. Indeed, the view was expressed in one of our interviews that ICTs should not really to be linked to the duration of their stay, but rather to the specific profession they work in and their high skill-levels (see section 3.1, p. 12 *et seq.* of the AspireE project’s [EU-level report](#)).

Structural discrimination is also visible in policy towards students. Students are profiled according to who has enough money and a certain skillset. Applicants (or their parents/family) must have enough money to pay for what are usually higher fees for international students (especially because they must show evidence of their fees having been paid, as stipulated in the 2016 [Students and Researchers Directive](#)), as well as have sickness insurance, be able to pay for their own accommodation, and without needing to work for a significant amount of time in the Member State they are studying in to support themselves – especially because they are not allowed to reside for purposes other than studying. On all these requirements, Member States can be even stricter if they so wish. This can have the effect of ruling out persons from lower social classes. Applicants must also already have certain ‘skills’ – they show this just by the mere fact that they have been accepted to study at a higher education institution, indicating they have already achieved good school grades at the very least.

Finally, although the EU has not established rules for investors specifically, investors who obtain residence based on an investment scheme under national law can access EU free movement rights and EU long-term residence status, and potentially also EU citizenship (and related rights) over time – all in exchange for nothing more than a large sum of money.

In many cases this lack of criteria disregards the requirement for continuous residence in the Member State or being required to stay for minimum periods to be eligible for permanent residence or citizenship. **This raises compatibility questions with EU law**, especially regarding non-discrimination, but also the principle of sincere and loyal cooperation laid down in the EU Treaties.

FINDING #3: The deliberately fragmented ‘sectorial’ legal framework has led to a level of complexity and lack of clarity to the detriment of legal certainty and transparency.

There are well-established EU general principles that must be respected regarding the quality of the law, including the principles of legal certainty and transparency. The EU’s [Better Regulation Guidelines](#) exist to ensure these principles are respected and there is a certain ‘quality of the law’ before, during, and long after legislative processes have been completed. EU legislation must be drafted in a way ‘that allows political decisions to be prepared in an open and transparent manner’, that it will be ‘effective’, ‘easy to understand, implement and apply’, and be coherent – because ‘EU laws and regulation cannot be adopted in isolation’. It must pay due account to the impacts of new and existing EU laws on EU Treaty principles and the fundamental rights of every person in the Union, irrespective of their administrative status.

The fragmentation and complexity of the EU legal migration framework comes on top of the inherently complicated picture of the EU legal framework due to the division of competences between the supranational and national levels.

While the competence over the admission of third country nationals to a Member State is shared between the EU and national levels, the split is not always a clean or straightforward one. Even when the EU does have and does exercise its power to legislate, there is a guiding principle that the EU must act to pass legislation only in line with the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality.

Furthermore, some existing EU legislation – such as the EU Blue Card – allows EU Member States to keep or run national schemes covering specific third country workers. The result is often that a non-EU national will often be subject to, or caught in between, two sets of rules running *in parallel*, as is the case for EU legal *labour* migration law because it is simply not comprehensive enough alone.

However, the EU's regular migration *acquis* now provides a ceiling of rights which Member States cannot go under. It is true that the Member States have exclusive competency in terms of putting a stop to any EU measures because they have the power to prevent first admission, resulting from a new subparagraph added by the Lisbon Treaty in 2009 (Article 79(5)). But this paragraph now expressly entitles the EU to legislate on all labour immigration-related policies *except* for issues covering 'volumes of admission or quotas'.

And while the Member States can generally restrict access to their territory, rendering some EU-granted rights by and large irrelevant, this has to be read and considered both carefully and practically. Capping regular migration entirely is not common, nor is it expected to become so, and it also means that this same subparagraph leaves '*the door open for the EU to legislate all the remaining facets that characterise legal migration policies for economic or labour considerations*', providing a window '*to move forward on the adoption of shared standards dealing with other administrative aspects of labour migration*'.

Finding #4: Third country nationals are prevented from adapting to real-life circumstances and transitioning statuses and have little agency over their own lives under current EU policy. This in turn leads to irregularised migration.

EU regular migration law and policy does not sufficiently consider the real-life circumstances and changing statuses of third country nationals who have moved to the EU.

EU migration policy frameworks often lead to a mismatch between the law/policy and the social characteristics and aspirations of mobile people. This causes incompatibility issues relating to the requirement to uphold the fundamental right to human dignity, non-discrimination, the right to decent working conditions, and the possibility for facilitated transitions as stated in the UN Global Compact for Migration.

To illustrate this, EU labour migration law does not cover a situation where a seasonal worker may become a family member of a person in the EU, that they may become pregnant, may wish to study or professionally upskill, or may face constructive dismissal (unless this is covered by *serious* 'labour exploitation') that leads them to become unemployed – all on top of not having any social security, tax, housing, healthcare, or other welfare rights. Nor does it consider that seasonal workers are denied the legal means to show that they have integrated, possibly over many months, into society (up to nine months per year) for several consecutive years, and the subsequent impact this has on their private and family life.

Indeed, the temporariness which is relied upon to justify restrictive EU policy and rights is not strictly speaking 'temporary' given that a seasonal worker can return several years

in a row. Perhaps the problem is that nine months is too long to really be 'seasonal' and that a minimum threshold of a five-month employment contract to benefit from labour exploitation rules does not consider that 'seasonal' work often consists of periods even shorter than this. This policy also does not consider that almost 40 % of seasonal workers are overqualified for the job they do and that the restrictive rules set out are likely to be contributing to this problem.

The selectivity of the EU's highly tailored labour migration policy amounts to a legal gap where there is a lack of effective regular migration channels, blocking a wide number of would-be third country national workers from entering and working in the EU. This may drive them to find other routes and venues which are not entirely designed for their specific 'migration purpose', and thus leads to an increase in the number of irregularised third country nationals in the EU. If a seasonal worker loses their status, for example in the ways referred to above, the fact that the status is lost means that they instantly become irregular migrants.

Similarly, students might not be able to complete their studies due to illness, disability, parental leave, or funding problems, and thus also find themselves falling into the category of irregular migrants.

This individual behaviour and individual circumstances are not considered by EU law.

Under EU tourism policy, irregular migration can be caused by EU Member States refusing to issue visas, even though the assessment is individual, to certain profiles when there are doubts about the will to return. This is due to a fear of allowing someone who has no family links, no job, no properties in the third country, has socio-economic difficulties, is young, etc. to stay, motivated by the fear that they will misuse the rules. However, this punishes *bona fide* applicants, including those who genuinely wish to visit family members.

Falling into irregularity can also occur due to EU tourism policy not considering real-life circumstances and changing statuses when individuals need to stay longer for *bona fide* reasons. Some people apply for a Schengen visa but due to its restrictive and temporary nature, or other reasons, often overstay. The EU Visa Code allows for Member States to extend visas to visa holders who are already present on their territory and who are unable to leave before the expiry of their visa for reasons of *force majeure*, humanitarian reasons or serious personal reasons under Article 33 of the Visa Code. It is, however, uncertain exactly how Member States' authorities interpret and apply these exceptions in practice, which once more creates a high level of legal uncertainty for third country nationals who may qualify in these situations.

Conclusions

This Policy Brief identifies important policy issues concerning the EU's regular migration policy and law, particularly the four key findings discussed above.

First, there is an objectifying approach to individuals that favours only the most highly skilled and wealthier migrants. This is due to an overemphasis on the otherwise legitimate economically-focused policy goals in this field, to the detriment of the twin policy goal of fair treatment and a rights-based approach to protect the rights of the individuals in question.

Second, the way that the EU structures its legislation results in a system that is so fragmented, selective, and preferential that it amounts to structural discrimination.

Third, the resulting level of complexity and lack of clarity erodes the principles of legal certainty and transparency to the detriment of the individuals in question.

And finally, because of the EU's policy and law, the individuals in question cannot adapt to real-life circumstances and have little agency over their own lives due to the legal constraints upon them, which in many cases can lead to irregularised migration.

To address the imbalance in the emphasis between those policy goals, the problematic structuring and complexity of the system, and to move towards a more humanising, non-discriminatory and rights-based approach towards the individuals in question that is in line with EU and international standards, this Policy Brief makes three recommendations that policymakers should take forward – more details on these can be seen directly below.

Policy recommendations

Policy Recommendation 1: The European Commission should give priority to **effectively enforcing and uniformly applying existing common EU rules and rights** under regular migration policies and across the existing EU sectoral directives. This also includes all the protective mechanisms which exist in EU law regarding access to complaint mechanisms and rights.

Furthermore, this should be coupled with the strengthening of **the EU's roles in monitoring and promoting the ratification** of all relevant international labour standards and the right to decent work for all workers irrespective of administrative status – not only in foreign and trade policies but also internally across all Member States.

Policy Recommendation 2: Similar to the areas of EU visas and border policies which have codified previously dispersed and fragmented rules, the Commission should **present a new legislative initiative taking the form of an 'EU Immigration Code' to simplify and streamline the conditions and rights for all third-country workers in the EU**. This would bring together all EU laws **into one single legal act**, directly inspired by the fair treatment paradigm enshrined in EU Treaties in light of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, international and regional socio-economic human rights and labour standards, as well as the political commitments in the UN Global Compact on Migration (GCM).

Policy Recommendation 3: Specific priority should be given to **transposing and streamlining the UN's GCM Objectives that call for allowing status transitions** in all relevant EU migration and mobility instruments. This is the most effective way to address irregularity in the EU.

The above-mentioned EU Immigration Code could include explicit provisions obliging Member States to allow these transitions, actively taking into account the changing life-circumstances of third country nationals in the EU.

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